

THE ROLE OF LEGISLATION ON PUBLIC CONTROL IN COMBATING CORRUPTION

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Abstract. Corruption is one of the global problems that needs to be addressed on a worldwide scale. This scourge undermines the political and economic development of any state and society. Today, corruption negatively impacts all spheres of society, weakening citizens' trust in state institutions and the rule of law. Undoubtedly, not only the efforts of state bodies but also the principle of direct public participation play an important role in preventing corruption.

This article discusses the role of public oversight in combating corruption and the legislative criteria for implementing such oversight.

Keywords: The word "corruption" originates from the Latin word "corruptio" and means "decay," "deviation from the right path," "violation of economic or social norms."

Currently, there is a trend towards the development of public oversight in the field of combating corruption, which serves as a "bridge" between state bodies and civil society institutions. The development of new institutional structures and the creation of organizational and legal conditions for public control aimed at combating corruption are of strategic importance for democratic states. Indeed, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 27th anniversary of the adoption of our Constitution, emphasized the following: "There is no more effective means of achieving the supremacy of the Constitution and the rule of law than public control. Indeed, unless our people stand firm against violations of the law, it will be difficult to ensure the rule of law, no matter how hard government agencies and officials try." [1]

The adoption of the Law "On Combating Corruption" in our country over the past period has marked the beginning of a new stage in the socialization of civil society institutions and their participation in combating and preventing corruption. Systemic reforms are being carried out aimed at ensuring the principles of "openness" and "transparency" in the activities of state bodies and strengthening trust in civil servants. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control" was adopted, which regulates relations in the field of organizing and implementing public control over the activities of state bodies and institutions.

As a consistent continuation of reforms to improve public control, the Public Chamber under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established with the aim of expanding the participation of the population in the management of state and public affairs, establishing close cooperation between citizens, society and the state, as well as strengthening public control. [2]

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6013 "On Additional Measures to Improve the Anti-Corruption System in the Republic of Uzbekistan" for the first time justifies the need to widely involve civil society institutions and other representatives of

the non-governmental sector in identifying the causes and conditions of corruption, creating an effective system for their elimination.

One of the main tasks and areas of activity of the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, established in accordance with the Decree, is to organize the joint effective activities of ministries and agencies in the field of preventing and combating corruption, representatives of state bodies, mass media, civil society institutions and other non-governmental sectors.[3]

The Latin word "corruptus" means "damaged," "damaged." Corruption refers to activities or actions that are contrary to the law for personal or group interests that harm the state or public interests.

The significance of public oversight in preventing corruption is understood as the fact that citizens and non-governmental organizations have open information about the activities of the state and its bodies and control this activity. This system allows for the detection and prevention of corruption.

To define the role of public oversight in legislation and public oversight in the fight against corruption, relevant laws and normative-explanatory documents should be adopted. As an example, it is important that the impact of cleanliness and openness laws be discussed. Such laws should make the information of state bodies transparent, define the main tasks of the public in their control.

Corruption is one of the important socio-economic and political problems for almost all countries of the world, and its negative impact is evident in the spheres of public administration, economics, and social justice.

Corruption weakens the ability of the state to fulfill its core tasks, loses citizens' trust, and hinders sustainable development. From this perspective, the issue of organizing and improving public oversight on a legal basis in the fight against corruption is of particular importance. The concept and significance of public oversight means that public oversight implements the oversight and control functions of society over state governance. This includes monitoring and analyzing the activities of state bodies and officials through citizens, non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs), the media (SMA) and other public institutions.

The main tasks of public control are: ensuring transparency in public administration, organizing public services in accordance with the interests of citizens, timely detection of offenses, including corruption, increasing the responsibility and accountability of state bodies.

The role of legislation in public control, its legal foundations for the effective organization of public control should be strengthened in the following areas: laws on public control, laws on public control strengthen the right of citizens to control public institutions and state bodies. For example, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Control" legally ensures public participation.

The right to access information and the openness of information are important in the fight against corruption. The Law "On Freedom of Information" guarantees citizens the opportunity to receive information about the activities of state bodies. This is an important foundation for the implementation of public control.

The role and tasks of public oversight are clearly defined in anti-corruption legislation and anti-corruption laws. At the same time, public control includes tasks such as disclosing information about corruption, exposing illegal actions of officials, responsibility and

accountability of officials. To effectively implement public control, it is necessary to strengthen mechanisms in the legislation that ensure the responsibility and accountability of officials. Measures such as declaration of income and expenses of officials, transparent tender processes are of great importance.

Despite the existence of problems in the practice of public control, legislative and institutional mechanisms, a number of problems are encountered in the practice of public control, the lack of legal knowledge of citizens. In many cases, citizens do not have the necessary knowledge to fully exercise their rights and powers. This reduces the effectiveness of public oversight. As a solution, it is necessary to establish regular educational programs aimed at teaching the population legal literacy.

The need to strengthen the role of the media The media is an integral part of public oversight, and it is important for them to disclose materials related to corruption. However, in some cases, media freedom may be limited, requiring improvements in legislation aimed at ensuring media freedom and supporting them as a solution.[4]

In conclusion, public control in the fight against corruption is one of the important foundations of a democratic society. If the harmony between legislation and practice is ensured, public control will become an effective tool in preventing corruption. The active participation of every citizen and organization in this process will contribute to improving the quality of public administration and building a fair and transparent society.

References:

- 1.Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг 25.01.2020 йилдаги Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси. // Интернетдаги манзили.: <https://uza.uz/oz/politics/zbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-shavkatmirziyeevning-oliy-25-01-2020>.
- 2.Батафсил қаранг. «Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Жамоатчилик палатасини ташкил этиш тўғрисида» ПФ-5980-сон. Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 17.04.2020 й., 06/20/5980/0450-сон.
- 3.Батафсил қаранг:Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг «Ўзбекистон Республикасида коррупцияга қарши курашиш тизимини такомиллаштириш бўйича қўшимча чора тадбирлар тўғрисида»ги ПФ-6013- сон Фармони. ҚҲММБ: 05/20/6013/100230.06.2020 й.